

THE IMPORTANCE OF HISTORICAL TEACHING METHODS

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Abstract: In order to teach students to think critically and creatively, as well as to develop the required skills and competences in them, teaching strategies are crucial, according to the principles guiding the development of education. The correct resolution of this complicated issue will have a significant impact on the responsible tasks in the secondary general education and special education systems.

Key words and phrases: traditional teaching, historical teaching methods, historical categories of thought, knowledge, skills, competency.

INTRODUCTION

The system of history teaching methods, in particular, has not yet been fully developed, which is a significant issue with teaching approach. Methodists have varied interpretations and categories for "Method" and "Methodical techniques" in the methodological literature. There are significant flaws in the practice of teaching history in the general secondary education and secondary special education systems as a result of the inadequate development of the system of individual and community education methods in the teaching methodology and the absence of a single opinion in this area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The goal cannot be accomplished by merely outlining the information that students need to retain, so care should be used while selecting methods and teaching strategies. It is essential to instruct pupils while also stimulating their cognitive activity and preparing them for practical actions.

Students can carefully memorize and retell the stuff they have studied using the first and second methods of instruction. You merely need to be able to memorize them in order to understand the ready-made knowledge that the teacher is explaining.

The key benefit of this approach is that it encourages students to pay attention and learn a lot of historical information in a short amount of time. However, this approach cannot guarantee that students' thinking, knowledge, skills, and capacities will develop or that they will become interested in studying history, particularly high school pupils.

The second method—problem-based learning or probe teaching—is more efficient than the first. In other words, while the teacher explains the historical knowledge to the students, he makes them think about this knowledge, activates their thinking activity, and increases their interest. The teacher poses challenging questions to the students, and together with them, he finds solutions to the problems. As they complete challenging and logical tasks with the help of their teacher, students gain the ability to think for themselves. All of this will aid pupils in developing their critical thinking and research work fundamentals. Additionally, utilizing a variety of techniques, educational and inspection work is done.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teaching and learning strategies as well as teacher and student-led thinking activities are common and significant aspects of these systems. The following groups can be used to categorize related teaching strategies: 1) Oral instruction, which is further broken into two categories: The following methods of instruction are available: a) oral instruction; b) instruction using printed texts; c) instructional technique; and d) practical method. The interplay between teaching strategies and various forms of students' cognitive activity, as well as their influence on one another, results in the interdependence of approaches within a system.

The secondary education system, which includes secondary special education, has found that instructional teaching is virtually never employed without a teacher's explanation, and that the teacher's explanation always makes use of instructional

resources. The use of technological tools, texts, and other practical tasks by students is directly tied to instructional and oral learning strategies.

CONCLUSION

All secondary education courses, including those in the secondary special education system, can be taught using this methodology. But depending on the unique characteristics of the content of each educational subject, particularly the subject of history, and its educational tasks, each of them is used in a different methodological style.

The educational process, in which the teacher and students take an active part, combines teaching methods and students' learning (cognitive activity) approaches in a variety of ways to build a coherent methodology.

Achieving a successful outcome in the process of education and teaching methods is unattainable if any one of this group of methods is ignored. While teaching and learning strategies are a part of educational strategies, they also comprise analogous strategies that are compatible with the critical thinking skills and personalities of teachers and students. But there is a relationship between teaching methods and educational approaches, with some significant similarities and differences. Teaching strategies are distinct from the didactic approaches used in all academic courses in this regard.

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